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Analysis of Solar Energy used in Myanmar

Sub Theme- Energy Resources

By

Dr. Zin Ma Ma Myo

Mr.Htet Lin Aung

Ms.Zu Zu Wut Hmone

Ms.Thin Thiri Soe

Republic of the Union of Myanmar

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Contents

No	Subject	Page
1	Abstract	1
2	List of Figures	ii
3	Introduction	1
4	Abstract	
5	The trajectory of the sun on Myanmar	1

In this report, solar energy used in Myanmar is analyzed briefly. Although the use of the solar energy can be received many advantages, using the solar energy in Myanmar is in the very initial state because of the expensive cost. In Myanmar, solar energy is mostly used in rural areas, where electricity is not available. Also solar radiation in Myanmar is presented in this report. Myanmar is a land of plentiful sunshine, especially in central and southern regions of the country. Applications of solar energy are described in this report. Furthermore, this report presents the Auk Pyun Wa village solar project that is an example of the use of solar energy in the country. The more the use of solar energy, the higher the living standard of the citizen because most of the people in Myanmar live in rural areas.

Contents:

No	Subject	Page
1	Abstract	i
2	List of Figures	iii
1	Introduction	1
2	Objectives	1
3	The trajectory of the sun on Myanmar	1
4	Solar Radiation in Myanmar	2
5	Solar Applications in Myanmar	5
6	Conclusions	7
7	Acknowledgement	7
8	References	7

List of Figures

Fig. No	Title	Page
1	The Trajectory of the Sun on Myanmar	2
2	Percentage of the area of Myanmar which receives Various ranges of solar radiation	3
3	Year Average of Daily global radiation over Myanmar	4
4	Solar Lighting and Solar Water Pumping Project at Auk Pyun Wa Village	6

1. Introduction

The Solar energy is definitely the future trend of energy. Nowadays, many households have converted their home to be powered by solar power system to take advantage of free and renewable energy from the sun. Solar energy is mostly used in rural areas in Myanmar, where electricity is not available.

Solar energy is also called "clean energy" or "green power" because it doesn't pollute the air.

Solar energy is used because of the following advantages;

1. Solar energy is very cost effective as the sun is free.
2. It is a renewable energy source.
3. The use of solar panels is environment friendly because of no pollution the environment.
4. It requires very minimum maintenance cost.

2. Objectives

Solar energy is used to take over the scarcity of hydrocarbon in future and to take advantage of free and renewable energy of the sun. The objective of this report is to understand the various uses of solar energy in Myanmar and solar radiation on Myanmar.

3. Trajectory of the Sun on Myanmar

The country Myanmar is situated between northern latitude of $9^{\circ}58', 28^{\circ}31'$ and the eastern longitude of $92^{\circ}10', 101^{\circ}11'$. The figure.1 shows the path of the sun is on equator on twenty-first March. On June twenty-second, the track of the sun is on Tropic of Cancer. On September twenty-third, the reached over again on the equator and on December twenty-second, the sun is on Tropic of Capricorn; then on March twenty-first equator again, making one complete cycle. Tropic of Cancer is transposing through Myanmar, on the towns of Teetain(Northern Chin), Tagaung(Southern Sagaing), Kukkhaing(Northern Shan). Standard Time of Myanmar in reference is positioned on the eastern

longitude of $97^{\circ}30'$. Total area or total square miles of Myanmar is 261228. Total approximate horse power on total area of Myanmar is calculated to be 123×10^{10} that is the sun's radiated heat power.

Figure.1. The Trajectory of the Sun on Myanmar

The cooler, dry season lasts from November to April and the hotter, wet season from May to October. During the dry season, Sunshine is plentiful average 7 to 10 hours a day. During the rainy season, Sunshine is average only 3 to 4 hours a day. So, potential available Solar Energy of Myanmar is around 51973.8 Tera Wh/yr.

4. Solar Radiation in Myanmar

Based on the yearly solar radiation map, solar energy potential of Myanmar was investigated. Geographical distribution of solar radiation was analyzed and the result is shown in Figure.2. It was found that 36 percent of the total area of the country receives annual solar radiation in the range of 18-19 MJ/m²-day, while there are only a few percents of the area with less solar radiation (< 15 MJ/m²-day). This indicates that most parts of Myanmar receive relatively high solar radiation. Figure.3 is indicated that the Year average of daily

global radiation over Myanmar. Since the reliability of the solar system is paramount, the sizing method used is based on radiation data for the worst month of the year rather than on the average daily irradiation over the year.

Figure.2. Percentage of the area of Myanmar which receives various ranges of solar radiation

(Source: Assessment of Solar Energy Potentials for the Union of Myanmar, Sep,2009)

Figure.3. Year Average of Daily global radiation over Myanmar

(Source: Assessment of Solar Energy Potentials for the Union of Myanmar, Sep,2009)

5. Solar Applications in Myanmar

In Myanmar, the following Solar Energy Indicators can be successfully propagated, both local, solar lighting systems, solar water pumping, battery charging and solar power generation. The solar applications in Myanmar can be listed as:

1. Remote-riding Village 3.8 kW
2. VAST South- West 7.2 kW
3. PV System for Carpin 0.5 kW
4. PV System for Radio 5.0 kW
5. PV Street Lighting 15 kW
6. PV Water Pumping 40 kW
7. Water Distribution District 200 kW
8. PV based Solar Refrigerator 90 kW
9. PV lighting from Health Center 15 kW
10. PV based PV system 250 kW
11. Erchin Dar Fielding Yupa Tawin Industrial 60 kW
12. Kanda/Raw B.H.S/Exhibit/7. Bya Toukha 5.38 kW
13. Aon Pya/Wa/Vedone Hga Pa Dand/Tru An/ya 205 kW
14. Yau Mya Aong Village 40 kW
15. Ching The Village 40 kW
16. Other village 40 kW

Figure.3. Year Average of Daily global radiation over Myanmar

(Source: Assessment of Solar Energy Potentials

for the Union of Myanmar, Sep,2009)

5. Solar Applications in Myanmar

In Myanmar, the following solar energy technologies can be successfully propagated; solar cooker, solar heating system, solar water pumping, battery charging and solar power generation. The current applications in Myanmar can be listed as;

1. Natha-myaing Village	3.6	kW
2. VAST Statin, Mogok	1.8	kW
3. PV System for Computer, Hakha, Chin State	0.3	kW
4. PV System for Radio Telephone Post and Telecommunications	3.0	kW
5. PV Battery Charging Station at Pale, Thongwa Township	0.45	kW
6. PV Water Pumping Stations all over Myanmar, Water Resources Department	40	kW
7. PV powered Solar Refrigerators under Ministry of Health	50	kW
8. PV powered Rural Health Centers under Ministry of Health	15	kW
9. Private owned PV systems(solar by various companies)	250	kW
10. Electric Car Factory(Yupar Theikdi Industried Co.,ltd)	60	kW
11. Kanyut Kwin B.H.S(Branch1), Phyu Township, Bago Division	6.66	kW
12. Auk Pyun Wa Valliage, Nga Pu DawTsp, Ayeyarwaddy Division	2.06	kW
13. Yan Myo Aung Village	40	kW
14. Chaung Tha Village	80	kW
15. Other utilizations	50	kW
Total	602.87	kW

As a sample project, solar lighting and solar water pumping project at Auk Pyun Wa Village, Nga Pu Taw Township, Ayeyarwaddy Division is presented in this report. Figure.4 shows the using of the solar energy project. It is used for Night time lighting and day time water pumping.

(a)

Solar Power Station

Solar Pumping System

Laying Water Pipes to Individual Homes

Villagers Conveniently Receiving Running Water at their Homes

(b)

Figure.4.Solar Lighting and Solar Water Pumping Project at Auk Pyun Wa Village

6. Conclusions

Since solar energy is renewable, free, no maintenance and clean the environment, it is the future trend of the world. Using solar energy, people living in rural areas can be improved of their living standard. Since the solar energy is available around the country Myanmar, some can use it because of the expensive cost. If Myanmar produces solar cells as a home made, the prices will be cheaper and can be used widely.

7. Acknowledgement

We wish to acknowledge especially to the Ministry of Science and Technology allowing to attend the 20th National Children's Science Congress. Furthermore, we would like to express our heartfelt gratitude to the people who inviting Myanmar to attend this congress and help us heartily. And then, we are deeply grateful to all persons who helped us directly or indirectly towards the successful completion of this report.

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9